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List of abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
BP	Best Practice
BIN	National Level Broiler Innovation Networks
BKH	Broiler/Net Knowledge Hub
BNF	Broiler Network Facilitator
C, D & E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
GP	Good Practice
GPET	Good Practice Evaluation Tool
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PM	Project month
OG	Operational Group
TEN	Thematic Expert Networks

Executive Summary

This document is the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan of BroilerNet, Deliverable 6.1 of Work Package 6. This C, D & E plan is the core document outlining the BroilerNet communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. It is a dynamic document that will be reviewed every six months from project month (**PM**) 6 onwards, and it will be adjusted following project outputs together with the experiences and knowledge gained through different communication channels.

The document summarizes all tools and means of communication that will be used for the various stakeholders and end-users and includes the various templates that have to be used by the project partners, of which examples are shown in the Annexes.

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1. Project objectives and introduction

1.1 Project objective

The overall objective of BroilerNet is to enhance the resilience and the sustainability of the European broiler sector, by creating space for interaction between science and practice and co-creation of ready-to-use innovative best practices (**BPs**) on broiler farms in Europe, at national and international levels. BroilerNet will mobilise all relevant Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (**AKIS**) actors in the broiler sector to work together to reshape the broiler sector for the future decades.

1.2 Overall project approach

BroilerNet is a European thematic network project that will provide a platform for dialogue, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and sharing of innovative good practices (**GPs**) across Europe. BroilerNet will focus on three sustainability themes: environmental sustainability, animal welfare and animal health management (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Overview of the BroilerNet multi-actor approach

Together with broiler producer organisations across Europe, these three themes have been identified by BroilerNet as crucial for the future of production systems. Around these themes, consultation among the consortium’s broiler farm organisations will be used to select the most crucial challenges that the broiler sector will face in the near future. Innovative Good Practices will focus on these challenges.

The BroilerNet project will run from August 1st, 2022 until July 31st, 2026. In total 25 partners from 13 European countries are involved; 12 academic partners and 13 Industry Partners from the broiler sector (Figure 2).

Figure 2: BroilerNet partners

1.3 Innovation networks and identification of GPs

The innovation networks are at the heart of BroilerNet. They will stimulate and foster knowledge exchange and integrate research and practice into innovation at national and European level among relevant actors in the Broiler AKIS. This multi-actor approach (Figure 1) creates space for interaction, knowledge exchange and joint learning to tackle real on-farm problems, leading to increased productivity and sustainability. Two types of networks will be formed; national Broiler Innovation Networks (**BINs**), and European level Thematic Expert Networks (**TENs**).

In total 12 BINs will be established that will map the broiler AKIS in each country, which creates an infrastructure to ensure that we include and mobilise all relevant broiler AKIS actors in the BINs. The BINs will be facilitated by a Broiler Network Facilitator (**BNF**) and are fundamental to the multi-actor approach through mobilising different kind of knowledge and creating safe and effective spaces for open dialogue and integration of different perspectives, leading to knowledge sharing and co-learning. The 12 BNFs will be trained as part of the project. The BINs will meet twice a year to identify and assess the most urgent needs for innovations and challenges faced by the broiler industry. They will collect GPs in each country that are proposed as innovative best practice solutions to the identified challenges, share, discuss and collectively learn to tackle the real day-to-day on-farm challenges and support networks on national level to develop their ideas further through forming operational groups (**OGs**) and to apply for OG funding.

Three Thematic Expert Networks (**TENs**) will be formed at European level. These are based on the three core BroilerNet themes (environmental sustainability, animal welfare and animal health management). Each TEN will be composed of representatives of research, industry, broiler producer organisations, advisors and veterinarians with interest and/or expertise in that subject area, including project partners. Representatives of the BIN will also be included. The TENs will have a dynamic composition; new actors will join them as the project progresses and different challenges within each theme are investigated. The TENs will identify priority challenges at European level and provide research- and practice-based knowledge on the state of the art to address these, screen the good practices identified by the BINs by implementing the Good Practice Evaluation Tool (**GPET**), a result of the BroilerNet Championship, and evaluate best of good practices in each of the themes.

For each priority challenge (eight per theme, 24 in total for the 3 themes), innovative good practices will be collected by the BINs through workshops and other network meetings. Then, these

selected GPs will be evaluated (including a cost-benefit analysis) and combined with the knowledge collated by the TENS. The farmers that have developed these potentially GPs will be selected for participation in a special presentation and will be invited to compete in a BroilerNet Championship contest. The national BINs and/or TENS (to be determined) will choose for the BroilerNet Champions. The BroilerNet Champions will be invited to host a virtual innovation tour on their farm, which will be captured as a video to enhance knowledge sharing with the BINs and the wider sector. This activity will build European broiler farmers' confidence to implement the GPs through enhanced dissemination, i.e. a science-based farmer-to-farmer approach. The GPET will use excellence, impact, probability of success and degree of innovativeness as criteria.

1.4 Dissemination beyond the project

Dissemination beyond the project will include two key activities. An online BroilerNet knowledge hub (**BKH**) will be developed to facilitate knowledge exchange activities within and between the BINs and disseminate knowledge across the European broiler sector, including countries that are not represented in the BroilerNet consortium. Further, BroilerNet will actively engage with existing and new EIP-AGRI OGs to harvest and integrate their knowledge and innovative solutions identified by the OGs in the project and to further disseminate their results on national and European level. This will be in addition to other dissemination activities beyond the project such as presentations on events, publications in sector journals, newsletters and on BroilerNet social media accounts as further described in chapter 5.

2. Objectives of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

This Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan (**C, D & E plan**) is the core document outlining the BroilerNet communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. This document is deliverable D6.1 of work package WP6 (Outreach and increasing impact) of the BroilerNet project and first published in project month 6. It is a dynamic document that will be reviewed every six months, and adjusted following project outputs together with the experiences and knowledge gained through different communication channels. Specifically, in the first revision (project month 12) the details on the Broiler Knowledge Hub, BroilerNet road shows and events, Good Practice Abstracts, webinars and virtual farm visits and Good Practice video's will be agreed upon.

The main objective of this C, D & E plan is to provide all project partners with a guideline that covers (1) the target audience of the project, (2) the tools and means for communication to reach them and (3) the general and specific obligations regarding dissemination and communication of the project that all partners must be aware of. Regional differences in terms of interaction and communication culture and the structure of AKIS in the project countries will be considered and added when updating this C, D & E plan.

The specific objectives of this C, D & E plan are:

- (1) To ensure that the project and the results are known to stakeholders and end-users;
- (2) To ensure that the needs of the stakeholders and end-users are considered in the communication means; and
- (3) To disseminate the project results in appropriate formats and dissemination channels suitable for each stakeholder or end-user to guarantee rapid uptake of knowledge and implementation of GPs.

The BroilerNet C, D & E activities can therefore be divided into the following tasks that will be covered in this C, D & E plan:

- (1) Internal project communication tools, means and obligations;
- (2) Identifying relevant stakeholders and end-users;
- (3) Define the best communication channels and strategies to reach stakeholders and end-users;
- (4) To ensure that all partners are aware of their communication and dissemination obligations;
- (5) To set up an evaluation strategy and to define performance indicators to measure the achieved impact;
- (6) To describe procedures for harmonised communication and dissemination from BroilerNet;
- (7) Outline all communication activities to be performed within the project to reach stakeholders and end-users by means of a C & D calendar (living document);
- (8) To initiate the writing of the sustainability plan to stimulate exploitation of the project results.

3. Internal project communication

3.1 Internal project communication

The internal communication pathways are aiming to ensure that throughout the duration of the project the collaboration between partners will be unhindered. More specifically, that:

- all partners have access to the same information at the same time
- all project developments are readily available and accessible by all partners
- no informational bottlenecks hinder flow between partners
- common communication procedures are followed
- there is no excess informational burden to partners

The project uses a platform within MS Teams (BroilerNet Teams) to ensure that all relevant documents are shared and accessible by all partners, at all times. The finalized versions of internal documents will be also uploaded to the BroilerNet Teams with limited access only by the project partners. Moreover, with the development and launch of the website and platform, finalized versions of deliverables will be uploaded on the public domain (EC platform).

The aim is to use the BroilerNet Teams to communicate, and to share documents of texts in progress. Furthermore, to ensure that communication is flowing between partners, the BroilerNet Teams communication is complemented with e-mailing lists will be utilized for communication. To that end, the WP7 will re-establish the interest of the all partners to be part of the mailing list and inform them about their right to opt out of the list in accordance with the GDPR provisions. The mailing list will be managed by the coordinator who will ensure its proper use and that all relevant emails will have the identification "BroilerNet" prior to the topic. Moreover, the coordinator will encourage partners to conduct all communication through one channel the BroilerNet Teams and in a way that all relevant partners are informed at once.

3.2 Project Advisory Board (PAB)

BroilerNet relies on the support and expertise of a high-level Project Advisory Board (PAB). This PAB consists of representatives of civil society and business or professional organisations whose collective interests cover the different facets of BroilerNet.

The PAB is established to reflect on all aspects of BroilerNet activities and to provide strategic guidance and support to the Management Team on these issues.

The following organisations have confirmed their willingness to participate in the PAB:

- (1) Association of Poultry Processors and Poultry Trade in the EU countries (AVEC)
- (2) Compassion in World Farming (CIWF)
- (3) Federation of Veterinarians of Europe (FVE)

Membership of the PAB will remain fixed during the lifetime of the project, although additional members may be invited to serve on the PAB on a short-term basis if circumstances dictate. A document with "Terms of reference" will be established to line out the mutual responsibilities of the PAB and the BroilerNet project.

4. External communication

4.1 Identification of stakeholders and end-users

The AKIS in each EU country or region are different and therefore targeted communication may need to be adapted to the specific regional situation and needs. However, there are common actors and structures that will be described below. As indicated, this C, D & E plan is a dynamic document and will be reviewed and updated every six months. With this updating, we will be able to identify the specific needs and situations in the different EU regions and adjust the communication strategy to ensure maximum uptake.

To prepare for the BIN's and TEN's a participatory actor mapping exercise will be carried out with all industry partners. This will result in an overview of the various stakeholders and end-users per participating country at the start of the project. The outcome of this mapping exercise will help to target the various communication activities. The outcome of this participatory mapping exercise will be included in the first revision of the current C, D & E plan.

The groups of stakeholders and end-users that already have been identified on a general level will briefly be described below. Table 1 identifies the main communication and dissemination tools and means for stakeholders and end-users as described below. This does not exclude that other communication tools and means will not reach the specific audience or cannot be used, but these are estimated not to be the primary source of information. Table 1 might be subject to updates in the revised version of the C, D & E plan.

Guidelines how to use the various communication tools and means will be described in paragraph 5.1.

4.1.1 Farmers and integrators

Broiler farmers and integrators are the most important stakeholders and end-users of BroilerNet, together with the farm advisors (see 4.1.2). Within Europe there are large differences in the extent in which the broiler farmers are independent (e.g., the Netherlands) or fully integrated (e.g., Italy). This also means that C, D & E strategies may differ between countries and regions, within and beyond the project. The participatory mapping exercise will provide more specific information on this aspect.

Broiler farmers and integrators will have an important role in the definition of the challenges and innovation needs for each theme and identification of GPs by means of the national BINs. In addition to that, specific communication strategies will be needed to reach farmers and integrators beyond the ones that will be involved in the project as partner or BIN member.

Table 1 identifies the four most important communication tools or means to reach farmers and integrators. The Broiler Knowledge Hub (accessible via the BroilerNet website), factsheets, EIP Agri abstracts and collection of GP's, GP video's, webinars and virtual tours, and events and road shows are the main channels to spread the knowledge generated within BroilerNet. These can also be used to generate awareness of the project and to attract farmers and integrators not involved in the consortium. Social media and sector journals can play an important role to spread the word on the existence of the project, and to guide farmers and integrators to the specific sources of knowledge.

4.1.2 Advisors

Advisors, such as veterinarians or advisors from nutrition companies are other important stakeholders and end-users of BroilerNet. Also here, the different structure of the sector in Europe might lead to different communication and dissemination strategies between countries, which will be further defined in the updated version of this C, D & E plan. Advisors have important roles in supporting farmers to change their management, and are therefore crucial for implementation of BroilerNet GP's in practice.

Table 1 identifies the same main communication tools or means for advisors as defined for farmers and integrators.

4.1.3 Other production chain actors

Other production chain actors are for example equipment manufacturers and pharmaceutical companies. They are more at a distance but nevertheless important with respect to innovative practices. The extent to which they are involved in farm management decisions varies. They need to be updated on innovative farm management practices as will be developed within BroilerNet.

Table 1 identifies the four main communication tools and strategies to reach these stakeholders and end-users. Social media are thought to be important to create awareness and attract them to specific content, which is available through newsletters, GP video's, webinars and virtual tours, and articles in sector journals. In addition to that, they will make use of the BKH for further information. Without doubt, factsheets and abstracts are important sources of information for other chain actors, with social media messages or the website and BKH attracting them to read these.

4.1.4 Policy advisors

These include policy advisors at various levels, regional, national and EU. Broiler production is subject to change in line with national and international developments such as the EU Green Deal. They need to be aware of innovative practices on a general level, to follow developments within the sector on the three themes addressed within BroilerNet.

The main communication tools and means are social media, the BroilerNet website, factsheets, abstracts and reports, and newsletters to generate awareness and guide them to more specific sources of information such as GP video's and the BKH.

4.1.5 Scientific community

It is important that the scientific community keeps updated with relevant developments in the field. As within BroilerNet major challenges and innovation needs are defined and GP's will be identified, they can use BroilerNet to keep up to date. The main communication tools and means are therefore the website, newsletters, factsheets, abstracts and reports, and scientific publications and conferences.

4.1.6 General public

Although the general public is not the most important stakeholder of BroilerNet, it is important to inform the general public to be transparent and keep the license to produce. BroilerNet can show that farmers and integrators are aware of the challenges on animal welfare, health and environmental sustainability and are continuously working on innovations on these three themes.

As main communication tools and means the BroilerNet website, social media, press releases and project videos have been identified, which inform people on a general level and can attract them to read more detailed information on other channels.

Table 1. Main communication and dissemination tools or means identified for the various target audiences (stakeholders/end-users). Note: this table lists the most important for each target audience, this does not exclude the use of the other tools/means for the specific audiences. Communication tools and means are briefly described in paragraph 4.2.

Target audience	Dissemination Tools/Means									
	<i>Social media</i>	<i>Broiler Net website & Broiler Knowledge Hub</i>	<i>Fact-sheets, EIP AGRI practice abstracts , GP data set and thematic reports</i>	<i>Press releases</i>	<i>News letters</i>	<i>Sector journals</i>	<i>Events and Road shows , conferences</i>	<i>Project video's</i>	<i>Webinars and virtual tours, and GP videos</i>	<i>Scientific publications and conferences</i>
Far-mers and integra-tors	x	x	x			x	x		x	
Advi-sors	x	x	x			x	x		x	
Other chain actors	x	x				x	x		x	
Policy makers	x	x	x		x					
Scienti-fic commu-nity		x	x		x					x
Gene-ral Public	x	x		x				x		

5. Description of communication tools, means, and guidelines for using these.

5.1 Social media

The BroilerNet project will open two social media accounts for general communication purposes: Twitter and LinkedIn. If considered relevant, and to be decided among the WP leaders, a Facebook account will be opened as well (see below). A YouTube channel has been opened to share all project and GP video's.

Wageningen Livestock Research will be the administrator of the social media accounts of the BroilerNet project.

5.1.1 LinkedIn

The project LinkedIn account is available at [LinkedIn.com/company/BroilerNet](https://www.linkedin.com/company/BroilerNet).

LinkedIn is one of the platforms with the highest number of EU Funded project accounts and EU Institution accounts. It is a social platform oriented towards professional purposes. It allows the user to create longer posts to publish articles, pictures, and videos. LinkedIn will be used to (1) generate awareness of BroilerNet, by posting information on project meetings, trainings, important milestones and (2) attract people to knowledge developed within BroilerNet by providing links to information on the website, BKH, and available via project and GP video's.

The WP6 team is responsible for posting LinkedIn messages. **All project partners** are responsible for providing content for regular posts. In the beginning of the project, posts will be once per month at least, which will increase to once per 2 weeks after month 6 and at least once per week after month 9. Posts will be in English, but can also be in other specific languages if needed. **All project partners** are responsible for providing translation into other languages than English. At least with respect to GP's, posts will be in other languages than English only.

5.1.2 Twitter

The project Twitter account is available at [Twitter.com/BroilerNet](https://twitter.com/BroilerNet).

One of the other social media platforms with the highest number of EU funded project accounts and EU Institution accounts is Twitter. It has a professional focus and a business to business communication structure, but also many non-professional profiles are present. Twitter allows short posts, and the publication of videos and pictures. This structure makes Twitter one of the main sources of news and updates for both the general audience and farmers, integrators, and advisors.

The WP6 team is responsible for posting Twitter messages. **All project partners** are responsible for providing content for regular posts. **All project partners** are expected to and can retweet the original message (which is in English) and translate this into their own language. Twitter messages follow LinkedIn posts with respect to content and frequency.

5.1.3 Facebook

If considered relevant, a Facebook account will be opened during the course of the project. This will be dependent on the preference and actual use of this platform by farmers and advisors which will be the target audience for this platform. Facebook will be used to communicate and disseminate the knowledge on the GP's.

The responsibility and frequency of Facebook posts will be developed in the next version of the C, D & E plan.

5.1.4 YouTube

All project video's and GP video's will be publicly available via the project YouTube channel. All video's should be preceded by the BroilerNet introduction slide and end with the BroilerNet end slide for video's as presented in Annex I. All general project video's will be in English and will be subtitled into other languages if needed. All GP videos can be in the language of the country where it is produced and will always be subtitled into English, but for GP's also video's in other languages will be produced. To this end, for each video a transcript file should be produced while making the video, which is the **responsibility of the partner in the specific country of the GP. WP6 Team** is responsible for the general project videos (and can outsource these to the partners).

Videos should be made by project partners according to guidelines delivered by WP6 (these include the maximum length, instructions for content etc). **WP6 team** will perform a quality check for each video before publication on the BroilerNet YouTube channel.

5.1.5 BroilerNet website and Broiler Knowledge Hub

The BroilerNet website is available via www.broilernet.eu (since M3). It provides a general overview of the project and work packages, presents the project partners and WP leaders and serves as a platform to access the knowledge generated within BroilerNet (see also Broiler Knowledge Hub below). People interested in news from BroilerNet can subscribe to newsletters through the website. Under 'news' the latest developments of BroilerNet can be viewed.

WP6 team is responsible for the website and content.

The Broiler Knowledge Hub will be the main source of information generated by BroilerNet. It can be accessed via the BroilerNet website. More information will be available in the next version of this C, D & E plan.

5.1.6 Factsheets, EIP AGRI practice abstracts, GP data set, and thematic reports

These include the information generated within the BIN's and TEN's on the innovative GP's to tackle the current challenges as identified for the three themes. Annually factsheets on GP's of the 3 themes will be developed and tailored to all partner countries. In addition, all GP's will be collected into one dataset. EIP-AGRI Practice abstracts will be produced for all GP's. The aim is to produce at least 15 abstracts on GP's and more than 5 general ones. For the three themes, annually three thematic reports will be written. These reports include scientific and grey literature.

Partners in all participating countries will be responsible for producing the factsheets and abstracts, **WP2-4 leaders** for compiling the GP dataset and writing the thematic reports.

These are important source of information from the project, and more specific timelines and responsibilities will be included in the updated version of this plan.

5.1.7 Press releases

Upon major events or milestones within BroilerNet, a press release will be made. This press release will be in English and can be translated into other languages by project partners. The format for a press release can be found in Annex II. There will be at least 2 press releases in year 1 of the project, and at least 3 in the following project years.

WP6 is responsible for the final version of the press release. **All project partners** are responsible for identifying topics for a press release and providing and writing content, and spreading press releases to media within their specific countries.

5.1.8 Newsletters

BroilerNet newsletters include a summary of the relevant developments within BroilerNet within the past three months. People can subscribe to the newsletter via the website and will receive it in their electronic mail box.

WP6 team is responsible for generating the newsletters, based on content provided by all project partners. The frequency of publication is once per 3 months.

5.1.9 Sector journals

Sector journals, either national or at EU or international level, are an important source of information for farmers, integrators and advisors. These are therefore important to generate awareness of BroilerNet and to disseminate the knowledge generated within BroilerNet. The national journals are in the specific languages. Articles therefore need to be written by project partners in their own language (or by the journal by means of an interview). Press releases are means to gain interest from these journals and to publish an article on the project results.

All project partners are responsible to share press releases with sector journals, and to inform the WP6 team of any publication on the project via the tool (see 5.2). There will be at least one article at the start and one yearly in at least one sector journal in all participating countries. In the updated version of these C, D & E plan the guidelines for these news articles will be more specific on responsibility, content and timing.

5.1.10 Events and road shows, conferences

The first event or road show is planned to take place in M18 the latest. At least one road show per participating country is planned. BroilerNet partners are required to participate actively in national and European stakeholder meetings. BroilerNet will organise one closing conference.

More details will be provided in the next updated version of this C, D & E plan.

5.1.11 Project videos

Project videos serve as a general source of information of the project, to attract people and to make them aware of BroilerNet. Project videos are brief videos in English with some general content, e.g., to introduce the project or the three themes. A transcript file is produced along with the video to enable translation into other languages.

Project videos will be made at least twice a year. **WP6 team** is responsible for developing the format and coordinating the video, which will most often be made by one of the partners.

5.1.12 GP videos and webinars

GP videos will show the BroilerNet champions by a virtual tour on their farm. Webinars will be held on the challenges and GP's, one per theme per year. The next version of the C, D & E plan will provide more details on these GP videos and webinars (responsibility, timeline and formats).

5.1.13 Scientific publications and conferences

Although BroilerNet is a thematic network, at least 3 scientific publications are foreseen (one per theme). The **leaders of WP 2, 3 and 4**, respectively, are responsible for these and will inform the WP6 team upon publication so that attention can be generated for these on the website and social media.

Scientific conferences can be used to communicate on the knowledge developed and the methodology applied within BroilerNet. **WP leaders** are responsible for identifying appropriate conferences and discussing the options for presentations and workshops with the coordinator and other WP leaders. At least five publications in relation to scientific conferences and workshops are foreseen during the course of the project. More specific information will follow in the updates of the C, D & E plan.

5.2 Input for monitoring of communication and dissemination activities

To monitor all communication and dissemination activities, all project partners are required to fill in an Excel sheet listing all these activities and information on the target audience. This Excel sheet is available from the BroilerNet Teams site and shown in Annex III.

The WP6 team will use the list of activities for general project communication on the website and via social media.

5.3 Visual identity, templates, and promotion materials

Within all communication and dissemination activities it is at any time required to use the logo and the other identity tools developed for BroilerNet and as shown in Annex IV. Note that in all communication, the banner with the EU logo and the associated text, as presented in Annex IV, should also be used.

Available templates are shown in the Annexes and available for each partner via the project Teams site, under the WP6 folder. Template use is mandatory. Where appropriate, instructions for use are provided along with the templates. In addition to the templates mentioned in paragraph 4.3, the templates as indicated below are available.

5.3.1 Templates for reports, documents, etc.

Regarding all reports, documents etc. written on behalf of BroilerNet the template for reports should be used as is available from the BroilerNet Teams site under WP6 and as illustrated with this C, D & E plan.

5.3.2 Promotion materials

Regarding physical meetings within BroilerNet such as BIN meetings, road shows and the closing conference, physical promotion materials will be available. The **WP6 team** is responsible to have these available (within the budget limits), **all project partners** should timely suggest what type of materials are needed.

6. BroilerNet communication and dissemination calendar

As communication and dissemination is key to ensure optimal knowledge exchange from BroilerNet to the end-users and stakeholder it is important to guarantee timely communication and dissemination activities. These are therefore summarised in a communication and dissemination calendar as presented in Annex VII. This calendar is a living document and also available on the project Teams site, and should be continuously updated by **all project partners**. **WP6 Team** is responsible for the production of the first version of the calendar and sending reminders for updates.

To be complete regarding the project output, Annex VI lists all communication and dissemination activities, targeted stakeholders and indices as defined in the project proposal.

7. Evaluation and monitoring

Evaluations assess the progress made towards achieving the BroilerNet project objectives and build an evidence base to improve the implementation of the current project aims. WP 6 will be responsible monitoring of the progress of the communication.

7.1 Impact measurement of external communication

The systematic monitoring of the communication of the project results will be done by **Key Performance Indicators (KPI)** specific for the different types of output of the external communication tools.

The KPIs and targets will be further defined in future updates of this CD&E plan.

Table 2. Key Performance Indicators and target per external communication tools. Where 'to be determined' this will follow in the first update of this plan

Communication Tool	KPI	Target
Project website	Website views	To be determined: #
Broiler Knowledge Hub	To be determined	
Social Media:		
Twitter	Number of posts Number of followers	To be determined: #
LinkedIn	Number of posts Page views Number of unique visitors	Once per month start Once per 2 weeks (M6) Once per week (>M9) #/per month #/per month
Facebook	To be determined	To be determined
YouTube:		
GP videos	Number of videos Number of views Number of webinars	BroilerNet Champion Video's:12 To be determined: #
Project videos	Number of videos Number of views	To be determined: # To be determined: #
Newsletters	Number of newsletters Number of subscribers	4/year To be determined: #

Press Releases	Number of press releases Geographical circulation	2/first year 3/following years To be determined
Fact sheets	Annual factsheet per theme	Every year: 3
Sector journals	Articles	≥1 per participating country per year
EIP AGRI abstracts		
EIP AGRI practice abstract	Abstracts	15
EIP AGRI general abstracts	Abstracts	5
Thematic reports	Number of reports	3/theme
Scientific publications	Publications	≥3 (one/theme)
Scientific conferences	Publications	≥5
Events and road shows	Event or road show Closing event	First ≤M18 ≥1 per participating country

7.2 Monitoring and evaluation

WP6 will be responsible for tracking the progress of the above mentioned KPI's. The progress will be the evaluating key of the communication strategy and will be used for updating this CD&E plan.

7.3 Updating CD&E plan

This CD&E plan will be updated every 6 months with the latest update in Month 42. These updates are meant to include experiences of the consortium with effectiveness of communication strategies so that needs of the stakeholders and end-users are met best.

8. Exploitation

At the end of BroilerNet, a sustainability plan will be produced to maximise opportunities to exploit the project results, including leveraging future funding. The responsibility for this plan is with the **BroilerNet coordinator**. Specific details will follow with the update of this C, D & E plan.

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Annex I – Start and end slide for project videos

These slides are required to use with each video. Some text and the pictures on the start slide can be replaced by pictures related to the presented topic.

Partner logo's (regarding e.g. Good/best practice video's) can be placed here –
otherwise remove

Annex II – Press release format

PRESS RELEASE
FEBRUARY 2023

News Title

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation **PROGRAMME** under Grant Agreement No 101060979.

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Annex III – Documenting communication and dissemination in BroilerNet

An Excel sheet is available to all partners to document all their communication and dissemination activities. All partners have the obligation to record all their activities here. The file can be found on the project Teams site, under the WP 6 folder.

Partner	Date	Publication type	Action	Title	Media with reference	Links to publications after release	Short summary of publication	Target Audience	Audience number
FMV	den 12 november 2022	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	BROILERNET: an international network to bring science and the broiler production sector together			Poster presentation of the BroilerNet project in a national scientific conference (CISA Congress 2022)	6. Scientific community and researchers	150,00
SFS	den 1 oktober 2022	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	Press release	Website	https://www.livmedaerfokus.se/nyheter/nyheter-om-nytt-halvbank-ycklingproduktion/		5. Supply chain actors	1000,00
SFS	den 1 oktober 2022	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	Press release	Website	https://www.svenskiveteinordning.se/2022/10/01/broiler-net-for-djurnar-och-hallbarhet/		6. Scientific community and researchers	3500,00
SFS	okt-22	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	Press release	Website	https://www.livmedaerfokus.se/17151-2/		5. Supply chain actors	1000,00
SFS	den 5 oktober 2022	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	Press release	Website	https://jordbruksares.se/forbruksgrip-sjuktat-eter-og-amal-fard		1. Farmers	7000,00
SFS	den 5 oktober 2022	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	Press release	Website	https://www.utbudet.se/svensk-fa-pel		8. All target audiences	10000,00
SFS	den 15 oktober 2022	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	Press release	Website	https://www.ja.se/7p22314690pt+1058m+3423		1. Farmers	10000,00
UNAITALIA	den 18 november 2022	S. Other	3.2. Publish in their respective news sections and blogs information and news about the development of the project.	Sostenibilità e resilienza del settore avicolo, partito II progetto europeo BROILERNET	Website	https://www.unaitalia.com/contenuti/la-resilienza-del-settore-avicolo-partito-ii-progetto-europeo-broiler-net/		8. All target audiences	10000,00
UNAITALIA	den 21 november 2022	S. Other	1.1. Writing and disseminating to partners and national press	Sostenibilità e resilienza del settore avicolo, partito II progetto europeo BROILERNET	Newstetter Unaitalia	https://mailchi.mp/31155494a0c0a/newsletter-unaitalia-19-dicembre-3073506		5. Supply chain actors	700,00

Figure 3: The Excel sheet to document all communication and dissemination activities in BroilerNet

Annex IV – Visual identity

The sheet below shows the items that can be used for visual identity of BroilerNet. This includes the logo (upper left) as well as the use of single items derived from the logo. It is mandatory to use the EU logo and associated text in all communication and dissemination activities. The templates automatically provide this, when not using a template, it is mandatory to add this.

FONT = TeX Gyre Adventor
Bold
Regular en *Bold Italic*

C=0 M=27 Y=100 K=0
C=15 M=100 Y=100 K=0
ZWART 80%

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060979

Annex V – PowerPoint Template

The PowerPoint template should be used for all BroilerNet presentations. The template can be found on the BroilerNet Teams site, under WP6.

Figure 4: The BroilerNet PowerPoint template

Annex VI – List of communication and dissemination activities in the project proposal

This Table lists the project communication and dissemination activities as identified in the project proposal, with the targeted stakeholders and indicators.

C&D measures	Targeted stakeholders	Targeted indicators
Factsheets	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	Developed factsheets on Good Practices (GPs) of the 3 themes annually, tailored to all partner countries
Good Practice data set	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	1 Dataset of collected GPs, adapted to all partner countries
EIP-AGRI Practice abstracts	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	Practice abstracts in the EIP-AGRI format, from all GPs harvested, ≥ 15 each for WPs 2-4 (i.e., ~one per country) and ≥ 5 'general' ones
Webinars	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	Webinars on selected innovation challenges, one per theme per year
Virtual tours	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	Virtual tours in BROILERNET Champion farms for 'Best of GPs' of the 3 themes annually
Thematic reports (TRs)	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (Europe)	TRs of the 3 themes annually, including scientific/grey literature relevant for Champion 'Best of GPs'
Newsletters	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	Newsletters to launch BROILERNET website, innovation challenges and related GPs (1 at BROILERNET start and 1 more every 6 months; in all local languages)
Press releases	All interested stakeholders, including the general public	5 press releases adapted to all partner countries (1 at BROILERNET start and 1 annually)
Posters, flyers, gadgets, etc.	All interested stakeholders, including the public	Same material adapted to all partner countries
Website	All interested stakeholders, including the public	1 New BROILERNET website
BROILERNET Knowledge Hub	All interested stakeholders, including the public	1 New BROILERNET Knowledge Hub linked to the BROILERNET website
Social media	All interested stakeholders, including the public	New accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook and Slideshare, plus a YouTube Channel
News articles	All interested stakeholders, including the public	Articles in national farming and trade press (1 at BROILERNET start and 1 annually adapted to all partner countries)
Scientific publications	All interested stakeholders, including the public	≥ 3 Scientific publications in relevant journals ≥ 5 Publications at agricultural and veterinary science conferences and workshops
Roadshows	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national)	At least 1 roadshow in each participating countries
External events	Broiler farmers advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	Active participation in national and European stakeholder meetings
Conference	Broiler farmers, advisors and policymakers (national/EU)	1 closing conference

Annex VII – Communication and dissemination calendar

This calendar is a living document and an Excel sheet with all activities is available on the project Teams site. Below is the example of activities in 2023 as identified by the partners on the project start-up. This calendar will be continuously updated and additional project years will be added in the next version of this plan.

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